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Comparative Production of Biodiesel Produced from Sand Box Seed Oil Produce from Heterogeneous Catalyst Obtained from Chicken Eggshell and Periwinkle Shell

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ABSTRACT

To reduce fossil fuel dependent and greenhouse gasses, biomass energy is in high demand. The sandbox tree is a common species in Abia State, but its seed oil is unfit for human consumption. In order to ascertain if sandbox oil may be used as a feedstock for the manufacturing of biodiesel, sandbox seeds were gathered from the Abia State local government of Uturu. The oil of the seed was extracted and then converted into biodiesel by Transesterification using Cao oxide catalyst gotten from Egg shell and Periwinkle shell. The quality indices (acid, iodine and saponification values) were determined, followed by physiochemical and fuel properties of the oil and methyl esters produced. From the experiment carried out, the sandbox seed has an oil content of 46.7%, iodine value (80.21g I₂/ 100g), saponification value (191.181 mg) and specific gravity of 0.8871. The effect process parameter (methanol/oil molar ratio, catalyst concentration, temperature, reaction time and agitation speed) were also studied to determine the optimal conditions for methyl ester yield. The biodiesel yield obtained by transesterification with Egg shell catalyst was higher than that obtained by trans esterification with periwinkle shell catalyst. The fuel parameters of biodiesel produced using Egg shell are; Kinematic viscosity (4.10 mm²/s), density(0.86 kg/m³), flash point (77 °C), acid value (0.38 mg KOH/g), cloud point (-1.5 °C), and pour point (-6.0 °C), while the fuel parameters of the biodiesel produced using periwinkle shell catalyst are; Kinematic viscosity (4.05 mm²/s), density (0.84 kg/m³), flash point (74 °C), acid value (0.35 mg KOH/g), cloud point (-2.0 °C), and pour point (-7.0 °C). Therefore, the properties of both methyl esters after analysis, complies with ASTM biodiesel standards. These results

suggest that sandbox seed oil is a good feedstock using both Egg shell and Periwinkle shell as catalyst for the production of biodiesel, to power Diesel engines without preheating system. These process parameters were optimized using response surface methodology (RSM) and analysis of variance (ANOVA). This investigation has demonstrated that oil from sandbox oil can be used to produce biodiesel. A full factorial central composite design was used to establish the significance of the various process parameters and their combined effects on the transesterification efficiency. The results obtained are in good agreement with published data for other vegetable oil biodiesel as well as various international standards for biodiesel fuel. An optimal yield of 96% was achieved with optimal conditions of methanol/oil molar ratio, 6:3; temperature, 60 °C; time, 180 minutes; and catalyst concentration, 0.6%.

Keyword: Comparative Production, Biodiesel Produced, Sand Box Seed Oil Produced, Heterogeneous Catalyst Obtained, Chicken Eggshell, Periwinkle Shell

1. INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of internal combustion engines and subsequent developments in engine technology have led to the wide spread consumption of petroleum fuels. Due to the shortage of petroleum products and its increasing cost, many efforts are put on the stage to develop alternative fuels. Biodiesel is a promising alternative fuel source as it is attracting an increasing deal of attention worldwide for it is currently the only renewable energy carrier which could directly replace diesel fuel in compression ignition engine [1].

Biodiesel is an eco-friendly, alternative diesel fuel prepared from domestic renewable resources. It is biodegradable and non-toxic fuel which has served as an alternative to fossil fuels [2]. Biodiesel possess several benefits over fossil fuels which includes lower health risk; due to reduced emissions of carcinogenic substances, zero Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) emissions, higher flash point (100% minimum) and lower toxicity in comparison with diesel fuel [3, 4]. Biodiesel degrades more rapidly than diesel fuel, minimizing the environmental consequences of biofuel spills. It has low toxicity as well as excellent properties as a lubricant [5].

Biodiesels are produced from edible and non-edible seed oils. Non-edible seed oils are majorly used to produce biodiesel [6]. This is due to the fact that non-edible seed oils are widely accessible and, more significantly, do not compete with food items, which may have an impact on the production and supply of food. The use of non-edible seed oils has been researched for a number of years with positive outcomes because cost is the primary concern in the manufacturing and selling of biodiesel (mostly because of oil prices). Because they include harmful substances, non-edible oils are unfit for human consumption. Plant seed non-edible oils are the most promising alternative fuel for diesel engines as they are inexpensive and eco-friendly viable alternative feed stocks for biodiesel production. Examples of non-edible seed oils are S Jatropha, Rocket seed plant, Pawpaw seed, Avocado seed, Jojoba, etc. [7].

There are 4 methods used to produce biodiesel from oil extracted from seeds and animal fats. The 4 methods are: Direct use and blending, Transesterification, Pyrolysis and Micro emulsion. In direct use and blending process, the oil is used directly to power a diesel engine or as a blend with Petro-diesel [8]. Problems such as carbon deposits, oil ring sticking, coking and trumpet formation on the injectors may appear after the engine has been operating on seed oils for longer periods of time [9].

Pyrolysis, often known as thermal cracking, is the process of converting one material into another using heat or heat and a catalyst. [10]. Small molecules are produced by heating without oxygen or air and cleaving chemical bonds. This procedure aids in lowering the oil's density and viscosity, which has a favorable impact on the engines' atomization [11]. The micro emulsion process is defined as thermodynamically stable, isotropic liquid mixtures of oil, water and compounds that lower the surface tension of a liquid and the interfacial tension between the two liquids. This process will solve the problem in viscosity and some other atomization properties of oil [12].

In the transesterification process (also called alcoholysis), a fat or oil reacts with an alcohol to form esters and glycerol. A catalyst is usually used to improve the reaction rate and yield. The catalysts involved can be acid catalysts, base catalysts or enzymatic catalysts. The yield of biodiesel through transesterification process depends on the nature of the catalyst. This is the most adopted method in biodiesel production [13].

The acid catalyst esterification process is first carried out before the base catalyst transesterification process, when the oil has more than 1% FFA (Free Fatty Acid). Acid catalysts include sulfuric and hydrochloric acid [14]. Base catalyst transesterification process is used when the amount of FFA in the oil is low (i.e. less than 1%). Base catalysts include sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) and Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) and Sodium Methoxide [15].

Alternatively, heterogeneous catalysts could be used in transesterification process with FFA greater than 1%. Heterogeneous catalysts such as enzymes include Titanium silicate, Anion exchange resins and compounds from alkaline earth metals [16]. Biodiesel yield depends on the temperature, reaction time, agitation speed, choice and ratio of catalyst and alcohol/oil ratio. The interaction between these factors affects the yield of biodiesel productions [17]. Methanol is the most frequently used alcohol although ethanol can be used. With the daily increasing need for diversification in energy sources, biodiesel production is being taken more seriously and various approaches have been adopted [18].

Owing to a better standard of living and an ever-growing population, the global energy consumption is increasing day by day. Net import of petroleum fuel is increasing rapidly. In this regard, the use of bio-origin liquid fuel is the best alternative to ultra-sulfur petroleum fuel, which do not only cause a huge dependency on other countries but also causes an irreversible damage to our environment [19]. As such, this has led towards this research in the production of an environmentally friendly fuel (biodiesel) from Sandbox seed oil as it is aimed at solving challenges faced by the use of fossil fuels when operated on diesel engines. The problem of waste management in Nigeria has posed a major challenge in the society. As a part of waste management, the idea to utilize Sandbox seed oil for biodiesel production was created [20].

This aids in the management of non-edible seeds which most people see as a waste product and utilizing it in the production of a useful resource in the form of biodiesel fuel [21]. Most importantly, the advantages of biodiesel fuel are of enormous benefits, which have motivated the birth of this research on biodiesel production from non-edible seeds.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2. 1. Procurement of materials

Sand box seeds were obtained from Ezianya Achara Uturu, Abia State, Nigeria. The chemicals and reagents were bought from Ogbete main market, Enugu and some of the

experiments were carried out in Chemical Engineering Laboratory, Gregory University Uturu. The apparatus and reagents used are: Glass Wares- (Beakers, Test Tubes, Flasks, measuring Cylinder), Soxhlet Extractor, Heating Mantle, Weighing balance, Viscometer, Oven, Steam Bath, Refrigerator, Platinum Foil Reagents n-Hexane, Diethyl ether, 95% v/v ethyl alcohol, Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH), Phenolphthalein as indicator, Potassium Iodide (KI), Glacial Acetic acid, Chloroform, Distilled Water, Sodium Thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃) solution, Pyridine, Egg shell and periwinkle shell, Acetic Anhydride, Hydrochloric Acid (HCl).

2. 2. Methodology

American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standards and methods were adopted for the entire production process.

2. 2. 1. Extraction of the Oil from Sandbox Seed

The seeds were removed from the epicarp, cracked and air dried for two weeks. Then the seeds were grinded into powdered form, stored in an airtight container prior to oil extraction. Solvent extraction method was adopted in the extraction of oil from the pulverized pulp using Soxhlet apparatus. The ground pulp was weighed and packed into the extraction chamber of the extractor; while the solvent (normal hexane) was poured into the round bottom flask of the extractor. The whole set-up was then mounted on a heating mantle and allowed to reflux for some hours. The condensed extract (oil and n-hexane) was heated at a temperature of 60 °C using a rotary evaporator to isolate the free flow lipid from the solvent. The extracted oil was subjected to heat in an oven at 100 °C to eliminate any moisture and solvent that may be present.

The weight of the oil produced was then measured and thereafter the percentage weight of oil produced from the seed was calculated using Equation 1.

$$BY = \frac{W_1}{W} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where: W = weight of sandbox seed used (g); W₁ = weight of oil obtained (g).

2. 3. Characterization of the extracted oil

The physiochemical properties of the sand box seed oil produced were determined following American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) methods, GC-MS and FTIR of the oil

2. 3. 1. Colour and flavour

Several competent, independent people were used to see the oil sample and determine its colour. Colour charts were used to correlate the colours of the oil. The aroma and taste were also assessed.

2. 3. 2. Specific Gravity (SG) and Viscosity

The viscosity of the samples was determined using a glass capillary kinematic Viscometer. The viscometer was tightly clamped on a retort stand, which was lowered into a pre-set digital water bath at 40 °C. The set up was allowed to stand for 20 minutes thereafter;

suction was applied to the other end of the capillary tube to draw the fluid to the mark on the upper meniscus level of the capillary tube. The fluid was allowed to run freely to the lower meniscus mark in the capillary tube. The efflux time for the fluid to flow from the upper meniscus mark to the Lower meniscus mark was determined with the aid of a stopwatch.

The test was Triplicated for each sample and the average taken. Kinematic viscosity was calculated using equation 2.

$$\text{Kinematic Viscosity} = kT \quad (2)$$

where: k = Constant of the viscometer expressed in mm^2/s^2

T = Flow time in seconds of the liquid.

Figure 1. Setting up the sample and Sandbox seed oil extraction with solvent.

2. 3. 3. Moisture content

Moisture content of the sandbox seed oil was determined in accordance with ASTM D2974-93 by weighing 10g of the bio-lubricant into an empty crucible. The crucible and bio-lubricant were weighed. The crucible with the content was placed in an oven at 105 °C for 5 hours. It was removed after 5 hours and reweighed after cooling to room temperature. The heating and cooling process was done repeatedly until the weight became constant. The moisture content was obtained using equation (10).

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = M1 - M2/M1 \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where: M1 = mass of the test specimen before drying (kg)

M2 = mass of the oven dried specimen (kg).

2. 3. 4. Acid Value

Acid value was determined in accordance with ASTM D 664-18 method. Sand box seed oil of 1g was weighed into 25 ml of isopropyl alcohol in a 250 ml conical flask. The solution was titrated using 0.1M potassium hydroxide (KOH) and 3 drops of phenolphthalein was added with constant stirring until a persistent colour appeared. The titer value obtained was used to calculate the acid value using the equation given below:

$$\text{Acid value} = 56.1 \text{ VN/W} \quad (4)$$

where: V = Titer value of potassium hydroxide used (cm³)

N = Normality of potassium hydroxide

W = Sample weight (kg)

2. 3. 5. Determination of iodine and peroxide values

The iodine and peroxide values of the bio-lubricant were analyzed using AOAC (2000) methods by dissolving 0.1g of sandbox seed oil in 15ml of carbon tetrachloride and stirring. The solution was mixed with 25 ml Wij's solution and stayed in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes. Distilled water of 100 ml and 20 ml of 10% (w/v) of potassium iodide were then added to the mixture. It was then titrated with 0.1 ml sodium thiosulphate using 10% (w/v) starch indicator. The titration continued until light blue colour was observed. The iodine value and peroxide value were then calculated using equations (5) and (6) respectively:

$$\text{Iodine value} = 12.69 \text{ B-S N/W} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Peroxide value} = 0.1 \text{ S-B N/W} \quad (6)$$

where: B = Titre value of sodium thiosulphate used for blank

S = Titre value of sodium thiosulphate used for sample

N = Normality of sodium thiosulphate

W = Sample weight

2. 3. 6. Saponification Value

Saponification value of the sandbox seed oil was determined in accordance with ASTM D5558-95 method. Sandbox seed oil of 10g was weighed into 250 ml conical flask. Potassium hydroxide solution of 25 ml was added using pipette. The flask content was thoroughly stirred and then connected to reflux condenser to boil for one hour for complete saponification. The cooled content was titrated with hydrochloric acid of 0.5M using phenolphthalein indicator. The value was calculated using:

$$\text{SAP value} = 56.1 (B-S) N/W \quad (7)$$

where: B = Titre value of hydrochloric acid used for the blank (cm³)
S = Titre value of hydrochloric acid used for the sample (cm³)
N = Normality of hydrochloric acid
W = Sample weight (kg)

2. 3. 7. Ash Content

After the oil was evaporated to dryness in a steam bath, the foil and its contents were placed in an oven and ignited to 600 °C. The foil was then weighed with the residue that resulted until a consistent weight was achieved. This allowed for the determination of the ash content. About 5g of the oil sample was weighed using platinum foil.

2. 4. Sources and treatment of the homogeneous catalyst

The raw eggshells obtained from Gregory University farm Uturu were carefully washed in distilled water for obtaining a better material for the catalyst preparation free from contaminants and then dried in an oven for 80 minutes at 100 °C to remove moisture present. The dried eggshells were then crushed with mortar and pestle to a fine particulate size then sieved with sieve and shaker to obtain <75 µm particle sizes.

The purpose of size reduction on the dried sample is to increase its surface area, which is a key element influencing the reaction's rate. Eggshell CaO catalyst was produced by calcining the finely ground material for three hours at 600 °C in a Muffle furnace (Carbolite HTF 1700).

The resulting CaO catalyst from chicken eggshells was then kept in a reagent bottle to keep it safe from impurities that could react with ambient air. A homogeneous sample is necessary for high-quality calcinations.

For CaO obtained from periwinkle shell a sample of the periwinkle shell was collected from Eke Okigwe Market in Imo State. The periwinkle shell was washed with tap water and was dried under Sun for three (3) days. And was subjected to thermal decomposition in a Muffle furnace (Carbolite HTF 1700) at 600 °C for 3 hours and at this temperature, it was subsequently grounded to powder form using pestle and mortar. The fine particulate size was sieved with sieve and shaker to obtain a fine powder. The periwinkle CaO catalyst obtained was then stored in a reagent bottle to prevent the CaO catalyst from contaminants by reacting with air in the environment. For quality calcinations, sample should be uniform.

Four hundred gram (400 g) of each of the crushed material of periwinkle and egg shell was measured in to 1000g concentration of methanol for 1 day, both the filtrate was filtered with White man paper, then filtrates of egg shell and the periwinkle was centrifuged and decanted to remove the remaining particles.

Figure 2. Showing the treatment of egg shell and periwinkle shell for bio- catalyst.

2. 5. Characterization of the homogenous catalyst

This was carried out using ultimate analysis, nuclear magnet resonance (NMR), and scanning electron microscope (SEM).

2. 5. 1. Ultimate analysis of the homogenous catalysts (egg shell and periwinkle shell)

The composition of Egg shell and periwinkle shell catalysts for biodiesel production comprises of varieties of elements and oxides, which are present in the biocatalyst, the Egg Shell Contains calcium (Ca), which is a strong element that's responsible for the catalyst's basic nature. From the composition Egg shells can be used as a heterogeneous catalyst for biodiesel production through transesterification process. While Periwinkle Shell Contain other elements such as sodium oxide (Na_2O), calcium oxide (CaO), potassium oxide (K_2O), and magnesium oxide (MgO). Other elements and oxides that may be present in catalysts for biodiesel production include: Aluminum (Al), Iron (Fe), Phosphorus (P), Silicon (Si), Tin (Sn), and Manganese (Mn). Biodiesel is a mono-alkyl ester of fatty acids that's produced through a transesterification reaction. This reaction involves vegetable oils or animal fats, an alcohol like methanol, and a catalyst.

2. 5. 2. SEM Analysis of the Catalyst

Figure 3. Showing SEM image of egg shell.

Figure 4. Showing SEM Image of periwinkle shell.

The morphology of the eggshell waste and thermally treated periwinkle shell derived catalyst is investigated by SEM. in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively which shows the morphological analysis of eggshell and periwinkle shell at different magnifications. The SEM images show that the prepared catalysts are porous structure. It reveals the presence of mineral aggregates with macrospores in both catalysts and they can easily bind or mix with methanol and oil ratio. According to the SEM images below, the carbonized eggshell waste and periwinkle shell treated are the results of the topology of the shells when characterized under a SEM. The egg shell shows a sharp grain-like view while periwinkle shell shows a wooly distribution of the mineral content.

2. 6. Transesterification procedure

Acidity greater than 1% has been evaluated in advance for crude sand box seed oil. This required neutralization of the oil with a methanolic solution of potassium hydroxide before preheating. Under stirring, a methanolic solution of 6.1% egg shell in a methanol/oil ratio of 6:5% was added. After 60 minutes of agitation of the mixture at 60 °C, a settling time of 320 minutes or more was followed to enable the reaction to be driven to completion by allowing the mixture to separate into two layers of biodiesel and glycerol. [22]. The glycerol at the bottom was drained off by gravity and the surplus methanol in the biodiesel was removed in an evaporator. The biodiesel was washed in distilled water to enable the further removal of impurities. The washed biodiesel was dried. This process was repeated using Periwinkle shell as catalyst.

The percentage yield of biodiesel was evaluated using Eq (8)

$$\text{Biodiesel yield (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Mass of biodiesel produced}}{\text{Mass of oil used}} \right) 100 \quad (8)$$

2. 7. Effect of Process condition on biodiesel Yield

Experiments were carried out to determine the effect of process variables. This was achieved by varying the variable in consideration and keeping the others constant. All the experiments carried out were done for both egg shell and periwinkle shell for comparison.

2. 7. 1. Effect of methanol/oil ratio on biodiesel yield

The biodiesel production process was carried out five times changing the methanol/oil ratio each time, while every other process parameter was kept constant under a controlled environment.

The methanol/oil ratios experimented on were 6:1, 6:2, 6:3, 6:4, and 6:5 After all the experiments were carried out, the methanol/oil ratio of the experiment with the highest biodiesel yield was selected to be used in further analysis.

2. 7. 2. Effect of catalyst concentration on biodiesel yield

The concentration of the catalyst used in the transesterification process is varied across five values keeping all other process parameters constant. The catalyst concentration in the experiment resulting in the highest methyl-ester yield is then kept constant in studying the effects of other process parameters.

Figure 5. Extracted sandbox oil undergoing transesterification to obtain sandbox methyl ester and glycerol.

2. 7. 3. Effect of temperature on biodiesel yield

The temperature at which the methyl ester is produced from sand box seed oil is varied to determine the effect of temperature on the biodiesel yield when all other process parameters are kept constant. After the experiments, comparisons are made to determine at what temperature the highest biodiesel yield was gotten. This temperature is then kept constant to study the effect of other process parameters.

2. 7. 4. Effect of time on biodiesel yield

The time within which the oil, methanol and catalyst mixture is heated during transesterification is varied across 60 minutes to 320 minutes for five different productions while the other process parameters are kept constant for all the experiments. The time resulting in the highest biodiesel yield is then kept constant.

2. 7. 5. Effect of agitation speed on biodiesel yield

The biodiesel production process was carried out five times changing the speed of agitation each time, while every other process parameter was kept constant under a controlled environment. The agitation speeds experimented was 400, 450, 500, 550 and 600 rpm speed. After all the experiments were carried out, the agitation speed of the experiment with the highest biodiesel yield was then kept constant.

2. 8. Characteristic of biodiesel obtained with optimum parameters

The physiochemical properties of the sand box seed oil produced were determined following American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) methods.

2. 8. 1. Colour

The colour of the biodiesel that was created was observed by a number of competent and independent people. Using colour charts, the colours of biodiesel were connected. Additionally, the smell was identified.

2. 8. 2. Moisture content

This is done to determine how much moisture is in the biodiesel that is produced. A known quantity of biodiesel was placed in a sanitized beaker that had been previously weighed in order to determine the moisture content of the fuel. The sample was cooked to 100 °C for two hours in an oven. After being taken out of the oven, the sample was weighed.

2. 8. 3. Acid Value

Biodiesel sample of 15g is dissolved in 50 ml bioethanol/diethyl ether mixture (1:1 by volume). The sample is treated potentiometrically with alcohol KOH. After each titration, a pH glass electrode that has been specially developed for non-aqueous acid-base titrations, is thoroughly rinsed with isopropyl alcohol.

2. 8. 4. Cloud Point and Pour Point

The cloud and pour points of the samples were analyzed by reducing their temperatures. Samples of biodiesel were introduced into a test tube with a thermometer inserted in it and placed in a refrigerator. The temperature of the samples was monitored as it decreased, the temperature at which the clear sample loses its sharpness due to cloud formation was noted as the sample's cloud point. Hence, the samples were linter cooled with an attempt to pour the samples at every increase in temperature [23]. The samples were inspected at every one-minute interval by tilting it horizontally. The temperature at which a sample could not pour freely for five seconds was noted as the pour point.

2. 8. 5. Flash Point

A pre-weighed porcelain dish was filled with 2.5 ml of the sample (biodiesel). After a few minutes of heating the biodiesel sample, a piece of paper was lit and waved across the heated fuel. The flash point was identified as the moment the diesel ignited. As soon as a flame was noticed, the temperature was promptly noted using a thermometer.

2. 9. Statistical design and optimization approach

The RSM model equation is represented in Equ. (9) to predict the optimal yield of biodiesel.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i X_i + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{ij} X_i X_j \tag{9}$$

The experiments carried out to determine the effect of process parameters on the yield of sandbox seed oil using activated eggshell and periwinkle shell gave the levels for each variable as shown in Table 1. The RSM-GA optimization technique was used to optimize the process input parameters used for modelling the transesterification of sandbox seed oil to biodiesel. The RSM model equation was run on a genetic algorithm in MATLAB R2015a to determine process variable fitness and represented on a best fitness plot function. The multi-input-single-output (MISO) architecture neural fitting design in Fig. 13 was used for ANN in order to estimate the ideal biodiesel yield and model the performance of the process factors [24]. The catalyst, methanol/oil ratio, temperature, reaction duration, and agitation speed are the multi-input factors; the single-output is biodiesel made from sandbox seed oil using periwinkle and egg shell activated catalyst. The variables were selected in order to examine how the input factors collectively affect the output variable.

Table 1. Range of process variables in actual and coded form at optimal biodiesel yield for egg shell and periwinkle shell.

Independent Factors	Low level	Medium	High level	-Alpha	+Alpha
	(-1)	Level (0)	(+1)	(-2)	(+2)
Temperature	55	60	65	50	70
Reaction time	125	190	255	60	320
Agitation speed	450	500	550	400	600
Methanol/oil ratio	2	3	4	1	5
Catalyst concentration	3	3.5	4	2.5	4.5

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Physical and Chemical Characteristics of Sandbox Seed Oil

The physical and chemical characteristics of sandbox seed oil are shown on Table 2. From this study, the percentage weight of sandbox seed oil obtained from the seed was at 46.07%. The value can be compared closely with the previous study on this seed by [25], who obtained 47.77%. The moisture content of the oil in percentage was 12.28% which is closely higher than 7.28% obtained by [26], but is still expected to be more stable than those oil with high value. The specific gravity, Ph value and the boiling point of the oil were also obtained to be 0.8871, 4.66 and 120 °C respectively. The acidity of the sandbox seed oil above 1% requires neutralization before it is used in diesel engines [27].

The saponification value was obtained at 191.18 mg/g, which is higher than 178.13 mg/KOH/g obtained by [28]. It can be concluded that sandbox seed oil is not of very high molecular weight and containing many short chained fatty acids. The acid value is 3.03 mg/KOH/g, the acid value of an oil indicates the quantity of fatty substances, and the higher the fatty acid presenting an oil, the greater the acid value. The value is comparable to that obtained by [29], at 3.11 mg/KOH/g, from the values obtained as the saponification and the acid value, the ester value was then obtained as 188.145 mg/g. The iodine value measures the degree of unsaturated fatty acid in an oil [30]. The iodine value; $80.21 \pm 0.40 \text{g I}_2 / 100\text{g}$, shows the unsaturated character of the oil. From this, it could be said that sandbox seed oil will not solidify at room temperature. The lower calorific value of the oil in MJ/kg was 47.27, higher than 39.07 obtained by [31]. The Cetane number was 56.80 which was also higher than the value 44.53 obtained by [32].

Table 2. Physio-chemical properties of Sandbox seed oil produced.

Properties	Sandbox Seed Oil
Percentage Yield	46.7
Color/Appearance	Golden Yellow
Density @ 40 °C (g/cm ³)	0.8871
Acid Value (mg/ NaOH/g)	3.036
Iodine Value (g I ₂ /100g)	80.2
Saponification Value (mg/NaOH/g)	191.181
Lower caloric valuen (MJ/kg)	47.27
Cetane number	56.80

3. 2. Fuel properties of Sandbox seed oil Methyl Esters

The physiochemical and fuel characteristics of Sandbox seed oil Methyl Esters are shown on Table 3 below, in comparison with the Diesel fuel and ASTM standards.

The key characteristic of biodiesel is its viscosity, which influences how fuel injection equipment works. The feedstock utilised has a major impact on the biodiesel's kinematic

viscosity, or KV [33]. The kinematics viscosity values of the methyl ester produced from the sandbox seed oil when CaO Catalyst obtained from eggshells and periwinkle shells were used separately as catalyst were determined to be 0.80 mm²/s and 0.83 mm²/s respectively [34].

Density is another important property of biodiesel. The density of biodiesel produced from sandbox oil using CaO Catalyst obtained from eggshells and periwinkle shells was 0.89 g/cm³ and 0.88 g/cm³ respectively, although there is no specification stipulated for density by ASTM Standards, this value fits well in the acceptable range of 0.860-0.900 g/cm³ [35].

The temperature at which a fuel will ignite when exposed to flame. An advantage of biodiesel over petroleum diesel is the higher flash point of the former than the latter [36]. The sandbox seed methyl ester produced using CaO Catalyst obtained from eggshells (ES) and periwinkle shells (PS) has a flash point of 150 °C and 157 °C respectively which are greater than petroleum diesel which has flash point value of 77 °C by 73 °C and 84 °C respectively [37]. The acid value of the biodiesel is the amount of FFA it contains, measured in milligrammes of KOH needed to neutralise one gramme of the sample. as the table shows. When iodine is formally added to the double bonds, the amount of overall unsaturation of a fatty material is measured in grammes of iodine per 100g of sample [38].

This is known as the iodine value. The biodiesel made from eggshells and periwinkle shells employing CaO catalyst has iodine values of 95.2g I₂/100g and 98.4g I₂/100g, respectively, meeting the required levels.

Table 3. Physio-chemical and fuel properties of sandbox seed oil Methly esters produced as compared with Diesel fuel and ASTM standards.

Proprieties	Diesel	SBSOMES (ES catalyst)	SBSOME (PS catalyst)	ASTM STANDARDS
Percentage (%) yield	-	85.7	83.4	-
Colour /Appearance	Clear yellow	Golden Yellow	Golden Yellow	-
Density @ 40 °C (g/cm ³)	0.832	0.86	0.84	0.88
Acid value (mg/KOH/g)	-	0.38	0.35	0.5max
Iodine value (g I ₂ /100g)	-	98.4	95.2	-
Saponification value (mg/KOH/g)	191.18	-	-	-
Kinematic viscosity (mm ² /s)	1.43	4.10	4.05	1.9-6.0
Flash point (°C)	63	77	74	93 mins
Cloud point (°C)	-15 to 5	-2.0	-1.5	-3- -12
Pour point (°C)	-7	-6	-15- -16	-15- -16
Cetane number	49.0	58.10	57.31	47mins
Calorific value (MJ/kg)	45.8	42.01	41.82	

3. 3. Effect of process parameters

3. 3. 1. Impact of Methanol/oil molar ratio on biodiesel yield

Figure 6 shows the influence of the methanol/oil molar ratio on the conversion rate of sandbox seed oil into methyl ester. The catalyst concentration, time, agitation speed and temperature for the reaction were kept constant while methanol /oil ratio was varied.

Using egg shell as catalyst, after reacting for 120 minutes, the transesterification process with methanol/oil molar ratio of 6:4 gave the highest yield while that with methanol oil ratio of 6:5 gave the lowest yield. The biodiesel yield increases slightly from 83.07% to 98.03% as methanol oil increase from 6:1 to 6:4 while a steady decline in biodiesel yield was observed as the methanol oil ratio was increased beyond 6:4. This decline is as a result of insufficient oil content to react with available methanol.

Using periwinkle shell as catalyst, after reacting for 120 minutes, the transesterification process with methanol/oil molar ratio of 6:3 gave the highest yield while that with methanol oil ratio of 6:5 gave the lowest yield. The biodiesel yield increases slightly from 86.00% to 95.27% as methanol oil increase from 6:1 to 6:3 while a steady decline in biodiesel yield was observed as the methanol oil ratio was increased beyond 6:3. Since the highest methyl ester yield 98.03% and 95.27% when egg shell and periwinkle shell respectively, were used as catalyst, were observe at methanol oil ratio of 6:4, this molar ratio is retained for the rest of the operation.

Figure 6. Effect of methanol/oil ration on the yield of biodiesel.

3. 3. 2. Effect of Catalyst concentration on biodiesel yield

In order to select the amount of catalyst required for the transesterification reaction, experiments were conducted, and the results are presented in Figure 7. From the analysis when egg shell used as catalyst, the methanol/oil ratio of 6:4, 50 °C and agitation speed of 400 rpm, the highest yield was observed at catalyst concentration of 2.5% (w/w) as 98.03% while the lowest yield 81.41% was observed as the catalyst concentration was increased to 2.5% (w/w). this could be to possible competition between the saponification reaction and

transesterification. from the analysis when periwinkle shell used as catalyst, the methanol/oil ratio of 6:4, 50 °C and agitation speed of 400 rpm, the highest yield was observed at catalyst concentration of 2.5% (w/w) as 95.0% 27 while the lowest yield 83.01% was observed as the catalyst concentration was increased to 2.5% (w/w). this could be to possible competition between the saponification reaction and transesterification.

Figure 7. Evaluation of the Impact of Catalyst concentration on sandbox seed oil methyl ester yield.

3. 3. 3. Effect of Reaction Temperature on biodiesel yield

Figure 8. Evaluation of the Impact of Reaction Temperature on sandbox seed oil methyl ester yield.

The impact of temperature on the % yield of methyl ester from sandbox seed oil is depicted in Figure 8. The outcome shown that, up to a certain point, the biodiesel yield from sandbox seed oil increases with temperature; after that, it decreases.

It was shown that the biodiesel output steadily increased as the temperature rose from 50 °C to 60 °C for the methyl ester synthesis process employing egg shell as a catalyst. The production of biodiesel steadily decreased as the temperature rose. Therefore, the best methyl ester yield from sandbox seed oil was observed at 60 °C to be 88.7%.

For methyl ester production using periwinkle shell as catalyst, it was observed that as the temperature increased from 50 °C to 60 °C, there was steady increase in the biodiesel yield. As the temperature was further increased, the biodiesel yield declined steadily. This sharp decrease at 60 °C is because the boiling point of methanol is 64 °C and so methanol starts to evaporate beyond 60 °C. Therefore, the best methyl ester yield from sandbox seed oil was observed at 60 °C to be 88.7%. Temperature of 60 °C was therefore retained for the rest of the experiment.

3.3.4. Effect of Reaction Time on biodiesel yield.

The Figure 9 shows the yield of sandbox seed oil methyl ester on different reaction time ranging from 60 to 320 minutes at 60 °C, methanol / oil ratio of 6:4, catalyst concentration of 2% (w/w) and agitation speed of 400 rpm. When egg shell is used as catalyst, it can be seen that the reaction was slow initially due to dispersion of methanol into catalyst and mixing for about 20 mins before the reaction proceeded very fast.

Figure 9. Evaluation of the Impact of Reaction Time on sandbox seed oil methyl ester yield.

There was a significant increase in the biodiesel yield between 120 mins to 240 mins but a steady decline in product volume as from then till 380 mins, the optimal biodiesel yield was recorded to be 88.7% and the minimum was seen at 120 mins to be 69.7%. When periwinkle shell is used as catalyst, it can be seen that the reaction was slow initially due to dispersion of methanol into catalyst and mixing for about 20mins before the reaction proceeded very fast.

There was a significant increase in the biodiesel yield between 120 mins to 240 mins but a steady decline in product volume as from then till 380 mins, the optimal biodiesel yield was recorded to be 85.7% and the minimum was seen at 120 mins to be 65.7% [39]. From this observation, it can be clearly said that under prevailing conditions of reaction, an increase in reaction time beyond 240 mins will not yield further increase in sandbox seed oil methyl ester. This could be explained from the view point of the reversible nature of the transesterification process as reported by [40].

3. 3. 5. Effect of Agitation Speed on biodiesel yield.

During the transesterification process, the agitation speed enhances the contact of the reactants, thereby causing the reaction to be initiated faster. The effect of agitation on sandbox seed oil biodiesel yield was observed by carrying out experimental procedures at different agitation speeds from 200 rpm to 600 rpm, maintaining other parameters at constant levels. Among these, 450 rpm gave a maximum biodiesel yield of 93.1% followed by 80.2% obtained by 500 rpm. For this reaction using 2% (w/w) eggshell catalyst, the effect of agitation speed on sandbox seed oil biodiesel yield was studied by conducting experiments at different agitation speed from 400 rpm to 600 rpm and keeping other parameters constant, among these, 450 rpm gave a maximum yield of 93.1% followed by 80.2% obtained by 500 rpm [41].

Figure 10. Evaluation of the Impact of Agitation speed on sandbox seed oil methyl ester yield.

3. 4. Biodiesel FTIR analysis

The FTIR analysis of biodiesel sample is shown Table 4 above and Table 5 bellow. The FTIR analysis showed different peaks corresponding the functional groups present in the sample. The peak at between 3500 cm^{-1} to 3000 cm^{-1} showed the presence of O-H stretching which is due to the presence of water molecules or phenolic group in the compound. The absorption band at 2787.422 cm^{-1} , 2886.911 cm^{-1} and 2998.896 cm^{-1} correspond to the presence

of C-H stretching vibrations of aldehyde, alkanes and alkene respectively [42]. The absorption peak at 1845.046 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of C=O stretching vibration of anhydride. The band at 1920.277 cm^{-1} and 1618.805 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=C stretching of alkene. the peak at 1420.436 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of C-H stretching of alkane [43].

Figure 11. Biodiesel FTIR Analysis Eggshell Catalyst.

Table 4. Biodiesel FTIR Analysis Eggshell Catalyst.

PEAK	PEAK INTENSITY	PEAK SHAPE	BOND	COMPOUND
841.0694	Strong	Broad	=C-H out of plane bending	Tri-substituted alkene
1420.436	Strong	Sharp	O-H bending	Carboxylic acid
1618.805	Medium	Very sharp	C=C stretching	alkane
1845.046	Strong	Sharp	C=O stretching	Anhydride

1920.277	Strong	Broad	C=C=C stretching	Alene
2121.931	Weak	Broad	C≡C stretching	Alkynes
2509.521	Strong	Broad	O-H stretching	Carboxylic acid
2787.422	medium	Sharp	C-H stretching	Aldehyde
2886.911	Medium	Sharp	C-H stretching	Alkanes
2998.896	Medium	Sharp	C-H stretching	Alkene
3167.455	Strong	Sharp	O-H stretching	Carboxylic acid
3578.582	Medium	Very sharp	O-H stretching	Alcohol
3792.477	Medium	Very sharp	O-H stretching	Free alcohol

Figure 12. Biodiesel FTIR Analysis Periwinkle Shell Catalyst.

Table 5. Biodiesel FTIR Analysis Periwinkle Shell Catalyst.

PEAK	PEAK INTENSITY	PEAK SHAPE	BOND	COMPOUND
1271.554	Medium	Broad	C-O stretching	Aromatic ester
1622.846	Medium	Sharp	C=C stretching	Alkene
2002.833	Strong	Broad	N=C=S stretching	Isothiocyanate
2581.922	Strong	Broad	O-H stretching	Carboxylic acid
2840.559	Strong	Broad	N-H stretching	Ammonium salt
3071.473	Strong	Sharp	C-H stretching	Alkene

Different absorption peaks were obtained for sample. C-H peak corresponding to alkene was obtained at about 3071 cm^{-1} with overtone at 1622 cm^{-1} [44]. Absorption peak of carboxylic acid was also observed at about 2500 cm^{-1} . The peak at about 2800 cm^{-1} correspond to the stretching vibration of N-H stretch of amine salt.

Table 6. Biodiesel GC-MS Analysis Periwinkle Shell Catalyst.

PEAK	RETENTION TIME	COMPOUND NAME	MOLECULAR WEIGHT g/mol	STRUCTURE	COMPOSITION %
1	5.216	Phenol	94.113		8.01
2	5.304	2,4,6-Cycloheptatrien-1-one, 2-hydroxy	122.1213		1.23
3	5.414	2-Propanone, 1-methoxy-	88.1051		3.14
4	5.529	Heptanoic acid, methyl ester	144.2114		0.27

5	5.718	3-Methylcyclopentane-1,2-dione	112.1265		1.65
6	6.358	2-Pyrrolidinone	85.1045		0.65
7	6.550	Phenol, 2-methoxy-	124.1372		2.46
8	6.638	sec-Butylamine	73.1368		4.83
9	6.755	1H-Imidazole, 1-methyl-4-nitro-	127.101		0.76

Table 7. Biodiesel GC-MS Analysis Eggshell Catalyst.

PEAK	RETENTION TIME	COMPOUND NAME	MOLECULAR WEIGHT g/mol	STRUCTURE	COMPOSITION %
1	5.214	4-Heptafluorobutyryloxyhexadecane	438.463642		0.09

2	5.367	Cyclopropane, octyl-	154.2924		0.13
3	5.479	Benzene, 1-ethyl-3-methyl-	120.1916		0.23
4	5.686	Benzene, 1,2,3-trimethyl-	120.1916		0.36
5	5.930	Cycloheptane, methyl-	112.2126		0.39
6	6.367	Decane	142.2817		1.44
7	6.729	5-Eicosene, (E)-	280.5316		0.56

Table 8. Independent variables and levels used for response surface design.

Factor	Name	Units	Type	Minimum	Maximum	Coded Low	Coded High	Mean	Std. Dev.
A	Methanol oil ratio	mole	Numeric	4.00	12.00	-1 ↔ 6.00	+1 ↔ 10.00	8.00	1.82
B	Catalyst concentration	wt %	Numeric	0.2000	1.0000	-1 ↔ 0.40	+1 ↔ 0.80	0.6000	0.1819
C	Reaction Temperature	°C	Numeric	24.50	80.50	-1 ↔ 38.50	+1 ↔ 66.50	52.50	12.74
D	Reaction Time	Min	Numeric	25.00	125.00	-1 ↔ 50.00	+1 ↔ 100.00	75.00	22.74

The correlation between the experimental process variables and the transesterification efficiency was evaluated using the CCD modelling technique [45]. Second order polynomial

regression equation was fitted between the response (Transesterification efficiency, (Y)) and the process variables: methanol – oil molar ratio, A, catalyst weight, B, reaction temperature, C and reaction time, D [46].

Table 9. Experimental set up for 2-level-5-factor response surface design and the experimental values for biodiesel production from sandbox seed oil using chicken eggshell CaO catalyst.

Run	Methanol/oil	Catalyst con	Temperature	Reaction time	Agitation speed	Biodiesel yield chicken eggshell (%) RSM	Biodiesel yield chicken eggshell (%) ANN
1	4	4	65	125	450	70.78	73.18
2	3	3.5	60	190	500	90.10	88.48
3	3	3.5	60	190	500	80.23	81.88
4	3	4.5	60	190	500	85.65	84.99
5	2	3	65	125	450	87.79	85.04
6	2	3	55	255	450	84.58	83.25
7	3	3.5	50	190	500	84.44	85.04
8	5	3.5	60	190	500	85.66	84.42
9	2	4	55	255	550	87.01	86.95
10	2	4	65	255	450	82.66	85.04
11	3	3.5	60	190	500	85.46	85.19
12	2	4	55	125	450	86.55	82.50
13	4	3	65	255	450	85.66	85.04
14	3	3.5	60	190	600	83.23	81.45
15	4	3	65	125	550	79.39	84.88
16	2	4	65	125	550	85.66	85.08
17	3	3.5	60	190	500	90.62	91.46
18	3	3.5	60	320	500	81.56	80.79
19	3	3.5	60	190	500	82.50	80.17
20	3	3.5	60	60	500	84.70	87.58
21	1	3.5	60	190	500	84.26	88.63
22	4	4	65	255	550	83.97	85.65

23	4	3	55	125	450	79.44	79.58
24	2	3	65	255	550	93.34	90.30
25	4	4	55	255	450	86.55	85.04
26	3	3.5	60	190	500	87.66	87.89
27	3	3.5	60	190	400	88.93	88.35
28	3	3.5	70	190	500	83.66	85.04
29	3	2.5	60	190	500	83.59	84.53
30	2	3	55	125	550	93.92	93.05
31	4	4	55	125	550	85.66	86.31
32	4	3	55	255	550	85.92	84.40

Table 10. Experimental set up for 2-level-5-factor response surface design and the experimental values for biodiesel production from sandbox seed oil using waste periwinkle shell CaO catalyst.

Run	Methanol/oil	Catalyst con	Temperature	Reaction time	Agitation speed	Biodiesel yield periwinkles (%) RSM	Biodiesel yield periwinkles (%) ANN
1	4	4	65	125	450	88.73	89.58
2	3	3.5	60	190	500	87.80	88.54
3	3	3.5	60	190	500	87.40	88.51
4	3	4.5	60	190	500	85.62	85.12
5	2	3	65	125	450	85.29	85.11
6	2	3	55	255	450	85.55	85.56
7	3	3.5	50	190	500	84.18	85.11
8	5	3.5	60	190	500	87.80	89.72
9	2	4	55	255	550	78.50	78.78
10	2	4	65	255	450	81.53	85.11
11	3	3.5	60	190	500	89.87	86.27
12	2	4	55	125	450	89.03	86.87
13	4	3	65	255	450	85.71	85.11
14	3	3.5	60	190	600	84.87	87.16

15	4	3	65	125	550	83.76	88.25
16	2	4	65	125	550	83.28	84.67
17	3	3.5	60	190	500	84.09	85.39
18	3	3.5	60	320	500	94.95	92.47
19	3	3.5	60	190	500	88.31	86.29
20	3	3.5	60	60	500	85.43	88.47
21	1	3.5	60	190	500	87.80	86.40
22	4	4	65	255	550	87.80	86.77
23	4	3	55	125	450	83.96	86.47
24	2	3	65	255	550	91.70	90.89
25	4	4	55	255	450	88.03	85.11
26	3	3.5	60	190	500	87.80	87.36
27	3	3.5	60	190	400	87.80	87.55
28	3	3.5	70	190	500	86.81	85.11
29	3	2.5	60	190	500	87.50	85.85
30	2	3	55	125	550	86.79	87.26
31	4	4	55	125	550	91.90	90.97
32	4	3	55	255	550	89.65	87.44

Table 11. Response Yield (FAME) from chicken eggshell.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	434.94	15	29.00	3.46	0.0003	significant
A-Methanol/oil	0.0140	1	0.0140	0.0017	0.9679	
B-Catalyst con	77.33	1	77.33	9.23	0.0078	
C-Temperature	2.24	1	2.24	0.2678	0.6119	
D-Reaction time	0.1380	1	0.1380	0.0165	0.8995	
E-Agitation speed	38.71	1	38.71	4.62	0.0473	
AB	16.44	1	16.44	1.96	0.1804	

AC	11.90	1	11.90	1.42	0.2508	
AD	57.61	1	57.61	6.87	0.0185	
AE	35.58	1	35.58	4.24	0.0560	
BC	48.09	1	48.09	5.74	0.0292	
BD	24.45	1	24.45	2.92	0.1070	
BE	0.1600	1	0.1600	0.0191	0.8918	
CD	22.85	1	22.85	2.73	0.1182	
CE	13.58	1	13.58	1.62	0.2213	
DE	85.84	1	85.84	10.24	0.0056	
Residual	134.12	16	8.38			
Lack of Fit	116.00	11	10.55	2.91	0.9940	not significant
Pure Error	18.11	5	3.62			
Cor Total	569.06	31				

Std dev. 2.34, $R^2 = 0.9751$, mean 83.60, Adj $R^2 = 0.9519$, C.V.% = 2.80, Pred $R^2 = 0.9044$, Adeq precision = 26.5086

Table 12. Response Yield (FAME) from Waste Periwinkle Shell.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	305.49	20	15.27	64.54	< 0.0001	significant
A-Methanol/oil	59.13	1	59.13	249.83	< 0.0001	
B-Catalyst con	7.56	1	7.56	31.94	0.0001	
C-Temperature	48.42	1	48.42	204.60	< 0.0001	
D-Reaction time	8.18	1	8.18	34.56	0.0001	
E-Agitation speed	0.0155	1	0.0155	0.0655	0.8027	

AB	0.4865	1	0.4865	2.06	0.1794	
AC	32.80	1	32.80	138.61	< 0.0001	
AD	2.70	1	2.70	11.40	0.0062	
AE	21.93	1	21.93	92.65	< 0.0001	
BC	15.90	1	15.90	67.18	< 0.0001	
BD	6.19	1	6.19	26.15	0.0003	
BE	0.5513	1	0.5513	2.33	0.1552	
CD	0.8327	1	0.8327	3.52	0.0875	
CE	2.65	1	2.65	11.19	0.0065	
DE	4.17	1	4.17	17.63	0.0015	
A ²	1.92	1	1.92	8.10	0.0159	
B ²	0.3758	1	0.3758	1.59	0.2337	
C ²	83.09	1	83.09	351.10	< 0.0001	
D ²	0.3841	1	0.3841	1.62	0.2289	
E ²	1.99	1	1.99	8.42	0.0144	
Residual	2.60	11	0.2367			
Lack of Fit	1.77	6	0.2950	1.77	0.8738	not significant
Pure Error	0.8333	5	0.1667			
Cor Total	308.09	31				

Std dev. 3.11, $R^2 = 0.9546$, mean 84.51, Adj $R^2 = 0.9121$, C.V.% = 3.68, Pred $R^2 = 0.8037$, Adeq precision = 19.5162

From Table 11 and 12 the ANOVA results showed that the quadratic model is suitable to Analyse the experimental data. The model in terms of the coded values of the process parameters for chicken eggshell is given by:

$$Y = 92.01 - 0.1983A - 4.34B - 3.76C + 2.73D - 4.57AB - 6.77AC - 0.1900AD - 5.89BC - 1.18BD - 0.8962CD - 3.26A^2 - 1.43B^2 - 3.31C^2 - 2.51C^2 \quad (10)$$

and for the periwinkle shell, is given by:

$$Y = 92.93 - 0.2817A - 4.34B - 3.51C + 2.98D - 4.70AB - 5.39AC + 0.56AD - 6.52BC - 0.6837BD - 0.1462CD - 3.14A^2 - 1.68B^2 - 3.19C^2 - 2.51D^2 \quad (11)$$

To develop a statistically significant regression model, the significance of the regression coefficients was evaluated based on the p-values. The coefficient terms with p-values more than 0.05 were insignificant and were removed from the regression model. The analysis in Table 11 for chicken eggshell shows that the linear terms B, C and D, the quadratic terms, A², B², C² and D² and the interaction terms of AB, AC and BC, are significant model terms but A was included in the model because of its importance. The model was reduced to Eq. (12) after eliminating the insignificant coefficients.

$$Y = 92.01 - 0.1983A - 4.34B - 3.76C + 2.73D - 4.57AB - 6.77AC - 5.89BC - 3.26A^2 - 1.43B^2 - 3.31C^2 - 2.51D^2 \quad (12)$$

Similarly, the analysis in Table 12 the periwinkle shell shows that the linear terms B, C and D, the quadratic terms, A², B², C² and D² and the interaction terms of AB, AC and BC, are significant model terms but A was included in the model because of its importance. The model was reduced to Eq. (13) after eliminating the insignificant coefficients.

$$Y = 92.93 - 0.2817A - 4.34B - 3.51C + 2.98D - 4.70AB - 5.39AC - 6.52BC - 3.14A^2 - 1.68B^2 - 3.19C^2 - 2.51D^2 \quad (13)$$

The analysis of variance indicated that the quadratic polynomial model for both chicken eggshell CaO catalyst and periwinkle shell CaO catalyst were significant and adequate to represent the actual relationship between transesterification efficiency and the significant model variables as depicted by very small p-value (< 0.0001).

The significance and adequacy of the established model were further elaborated by a high value of coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.9751 and adj. R² value of 0.9519 for chicken eggshell and coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.9546 and adj. R² value of 0.9121 for waste periwinkle shell [47].

This means that the model explains 97.51% and 95.46% of the variation in the experimental data for FAME from chicken eggshell and periwinkle shell respectively. The adequate correlation between the two experimental values further showed the adequacy of the model [48].

3. 5. Response surface methodology and result discussion

The interactive effects of the process variables on the transesterification efficiency were studied by plotting three-dimensional surface curves against any two independent variables, while keeping other variables at their central (0) level. The 3D curves of the response (transesterification efficiency) from the interactions between the variables are shown in Figs. 13-32 [49].

The response surface curves were plotted to understand the interaction of the variables and to determine the optimum level of each variable for maximum response [50]. The elliptical

shape of the curves indicates a good interaction of the two variables and circular shape indicates no interaction between the variables.

The curves obtained in this study showed that there is a relative significant interaction between all the variables. Optimum conditions were also obtained from the response surface plots. The stationary point or central point is the point at which the slope of the contour is zero in all directions.

The coordinates of the central point within the highest contour levels in each of the plots will correspond to the optimum values of the respective variables [51]. The maximum predicted yield is indicated by the surface confined in the smallest curve of the contour diagram. The optimum values of the variables were: reaction temperature, 48 °C; reaction time, 96 min; catalyst weight 0.47% and methanol oil molar ratio of 10:1.

The predicted response value at these optimum values was 96.92% when chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst was used [52].

Also, the optimum values of the variables for the waste periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst were: reaction temperature, 46 °C; reaction time, 71 min; catalyst weight 0.47% and methanol oil molar ratio of 10:1. The predicted response value at these optimum values was 95.47%. This showed that the model correctly explains the influence of the process variables on the production of FAME from sandbox seed oil [53].

The lack of fit test with p-value of 0.7517 and 0.5349 for chicken eggshell and waste periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst respectively, which is not significant (p-value > 0.05 is not significant) showed that the model satisfactorily fitted to the experimental data. Insignificant lack of fit is mostly needed because significant lack

Figure 13. Surface plots between catalyst concentration and methanol/oil ratio against biodiesel yield for egg shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 14. Surface plot between temperature and methanol/oil ratio against biodiesel yield for waste egg shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 15. Surface plots between reaction time and methanol/oil ratio against biodiesel yield for waste egg shell CaO catalyst.

Figure 16. Surface plot between agitation speed and methanol oil ratio against biodiesel yield for waste egg shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 17. Surface plot between temperature and catalyst concentration against biodiesel yield for egg shell derived catalyst.

Figure 18. Surface plot between reaction time and catalyst concentration against biodiesel yield for egg shell derived from CaO catalyst.

Figure 19. Surface plot between agitation speed and catalyst concentration against biodiesel yield for egg shell derived from CaO catalyst.

Figure 20. Surface plot between reaction time and temperature against biodiesel yield for egg shell derived from CaO catalyst.

Figure 21. Surface plot between agitation speed and temperature against biodiesel yield for eggshell derived from CaO catalyst.

Figure 22. Surface plot between agitation speed and reaction time against biodiesel yield for eggshell derived from CaO catalyst.

Figure 23. Surface plots between catalyst concentration and methanol/oil ratio against biodiesel yield for periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 24. Surface plot between temperature and methanol/oil ratio against biodiesel yield for periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 25. Surface plot between reaction time and methanol/oil ratio against biodiesel yield for periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 26. Surface plot between agitation speed and methanol/oil ratio against biodiesel yield for periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst

Figure 27. Surface plot between temperature and methanol/oil ratio against biodiesel yield for periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst

Figure 28. Surface plot between reaction time and catalyst concentration against biodiesel yield for periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst

Figure 29. Surface plot between agitation speed and catalyst concentration against biodiesel yield for periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst

Figure 30. Surface plot between reaction time and temperature concentration against biodiesel yield for periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 31. Surface plot between agitation speed and temperature concentration against biodiesel yield for periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 32. Surface plot between agitation speed and reaction time against biodiesel yield for waste periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 33. Predicted versus actual FAME yield from chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst.

Biodiesel yield perwinkle

Color points by value of Biodiesel yield perwinkle:

77.5 94.95

Figure 34. Predicted versus actual FAME yield from waste periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst.

In addition, investigation on residuals to validate the adequacy of the model was performed. Residual is the difference between the observed response and predicted response. [54]. This analysis was examined using the normal probability plot of residuals as shown in Fig. 33 and Fig. 34 for eggshell derived catalyst and waste periwinkle shell derived catalyst respectively;

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

55.2 97

Figure 35. Normal probability plots of the residual for chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst.

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

Figure 36. Normal probability plots of the residual for waste periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst.

The plot of their residual versus predicted response shown in Fig. 35 and Fig 36 respectively. The normal probability plot of the residuals shows that the errors are distributed normally in a straight line and insignificant. [55]. On the other hand, the plot of residuals versus predicted response showed a structure less plot suggesting that the model is adequate and that the model does not show any violation of the independence or constant variance assumption hence conforming to the literature. [56].

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

Figure 37. Plot of residual versus predicted response for chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst.

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

54.2 97

Figure 38. Plot of residual versus predicted response for waste periwinkle shell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 39. ANN Regression plot analysis for prediction of biodiesel yield using fifteen neurons.

Figure 40. Histogram showing error distribution of experimented data and predicted data on MISO model.

Figure 41. Training error curve for biodiesel yield prediction using fifteen neurons.

Figure 42. ANN Regression plot analysis for prediction of biodiesel yield using fifteen neurons.

Figure 43. Histogram showing error distribution of experimented data and predicted data on MISO model.

Figure 44. Training error curve for biodiesel yield prediction using fifteen neurons.

3. 6. Kinetics

The main task of this part of this project was to investigate the parametric effects, including reaction temperature, reaction time, methanol/oil ratio and catalyst concentration on of the biodiesel conversion profile and reaction rate when using CaO from chicken eggshell and waste periwinkle shell as a catalyst [57].

The biodiesel conversion performance was evaluated in terms of FAME content (wt. %) of the reaction product as a function of reaction time. The change in FAME content with time provided an insight into the effects of these reaction parameters on the biodiesel conversion rate. It should be noted that an agitation speed of 200 rpm was chosen in this study because the speed is adequate for facilitating the reaction between oil from sandbox seed and methanol but gentle enough to clearly reveal crucial information on the advance of biodiesel conversion with the reaction time.

3. 6. 1. Effect of reaction temperature

The experiment shows the effect of reaction temperature on the FAME content as a function of reaction time. A catalyst concentration from chicken eggshell and periwinkle shell at 0.6 wt.% were studied at four different temperatures: 25 °C, 35 °C, 50 °C, and 65 °C [58].

It is clear that, regardless of the catalyst concentration, raising the reaction temperature caused the biodiesel conversion to proceed at a greater rate as indicated by a faster increase in FAME content, especially with CaO catalyst from chicken eggshell.

Figure 45. Effect of temperature on the conversion profile at 0.6 wt.% CaO from waste periwinkle shell (Methanol/oil = 9:1(molar ratio); mixing speed = 200 rpm).

Figure 46. Effect of temperature on the conversion profile at 0.6 wt.% CaO from chicken eggshell (Methanol/oil = 9:1 (molar ratio); mixing speed = 200 rpm).

For instance, in Figure 45, at 0.6 wt.% catalyst concentration, a FAME content of 85 wt.% was achieved within 10 min at 65 °C while it took as long as 110 min to reach the same conversion level at 25 °C. The increased rate of conversion with temperature is probably caused by two main factors:

- 1) An increase in kinetic reaction rate of transesterification reaction with temperature
- 2) A reduction in viscosity of feedstock oil with temperature that helps promote ultimate mixing between oil and methanol.

From Figures 45 and 46, conversion profiles at lower temperatures (i.e., 25 °C, 35 °C) appear to have two distinct conversion regions: slow conversion for FAME content below 20 wt.% and rapid conversion for content above 20 wt.%. [59].

The slow conversion region is an indication of poor mixing between feedstock oil (with low FAME content) and methanol, which was probably caused by the large difference in viscosity between these two reactant phases. For instance, kinematic viscosity of oil from sandbox seed at 40 °C is 36 mm²/s whereas methanol viscosity is only 0.59 mm²/s [60].

As the conversion progressed, the increasing content of FAME (with kinematic viscosity of 5 mm²/s at 40 °C) caused the viscosity of oil phase to decrease significantly, resulting in improved mixing between oil and methanol, which in turn promoting rapid conversion as seen in the conversion profiles at the low temperatures in Figures 41 and 42.

In contrast, at a high temperature, there was no dramatic change in the conversion rate. It appears from the profiles that the conversion at 50 °C and 65 °C proceeded rapidly as soon as the reaction started [61].

This simply demonstrates that the negative impact of viscosity observed at the low reaction temperature was eliminated at the high temperature, offering an improvement in the rate of conversion.

In addition to the rate of conversion, Figures 45 and 46 also provide important information on the maximum conversion level where the FAME content reaches the highest value and remains relatively constant as time progresses. They show that the maximum FAME content ranges from 80 to 90 wt.% regardless of the catalyst used and reaction temperature.

3. 6. 2. Effect of Catalyst Concentration

Figures 47 and 48 show the effect of CaO concentration on the conversion profile of the transesterification reaction at four reaction temperatures: 25 °C, 35 °C, 50 °C, and 65 °C.

In general, an increase in the catalyst concentration offers a higher rate of conversion, as indicated by the shorter reaction time, for achieving the maximum level of FAME content.

As shown in Figure 47, at 25 °C, the reaction required about 50 minutes to yield the maximum conversion of 79 wt.% when the catalyst concentration was 0.2 wt.%. As the catalyst concentration increased to 0.6 wt.% and even 1.0 wt. %, the reaction time required was reduced to 20 minutes and 10 minutes, respectively.

At 35 °C, in Figure 48, the maximum conversion for 0.2 wt.% catalyst was achieved within 120 minutes while the catalyst concentrations of 0.6wt.% and 1.0 wt.% offered a shorter reaction times of 50 and 30 minutes, respectively. Therefore, the conversion rate increased as the concentration of catalyst increased [62].

Figure 47. Effect of catalyst concentration on the conversion profile at 25 °C using CaO from chicken eggshell (Methanol/oil = 9:1 (molar ratio); mixing speed = 200 rpm).

Figure 48. Effect of catalyst concentration on the conversion profile at 25 °C using CaO from waste periwinkle shell (Methanol/oil = 9:1 (molar ratio); mixing speed = 200 rpm).

3. 6. 3. Effect of the FFA and moisture contents

All materials should be significantly anhydrous for the alkali-catalyzed transesterification because the feedstock is highly sensitive to the FFA content [63]. FFA and water together have the potential to react negatively with the catalyst and result in soaps. As a result, the catalyst's efficacy is diminished, and the reaction mixture becomes more viscous due to the soaps that are produced. Gels will form as a result of high viscosity, making the latter glycerol separation challenging.

According to [64], the FFA and moisture contents are crucial factors in assessing the transesterification process' viability. It is recommended that the feedstock utilised in the transesterification process have as little FFA as feasible, usually less than 1%.

3. 6. 4. Effect of the molar ratio of alcohol to triglyceride

Another significant element influencing the biodiesel output is the molar ratio of alcohol to triglycerides. Equation 2. states that in order to produce three moles of fatty acid alkyl esters and one mole of glycerol, the transesterification reaction needs three moles of alcohol and one mole of triglyceride.

However, a significant amount of extra alcohol is needed to promote the reaction since transesterification is an equilibrium reaction [65]. The highest conversions, 96.92% and 95.47%, were obtained at a 10:1 molar ratio of alcohol to oil when CaO catalyst from chicken eggshell and periwinkle shell were used, respectively. This project examined the effects of various molar ratios of alcohol to triglyceride from 1:1 to 12:1 on the transesterification reaction using oil from sandbox seed.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this research, a study of the comparative production of biodiesel using carbon oxide (CaO) biocatalyst obtained from chicken eggshell and periwinkle shells were used to determine the particular catalyst that gives a higher yield of biodiesel. The kernel sandbox seed have a high lipid potential of 46.7%.

This oil has good physiochemical and energy characteristics, but it is not recommended for direct use in diesel engines due to its high acidity and density. In comparing the sandbox seed methyl ester yield when Egg shell and periwinkle shell were used. An optimization of the sandbox seed oil transesterification reaction parameters was carried out by response surface methodology (RSM).

The process parameters for transesterification reaction such as: methanol oil molar ratio, CaO catalyst effect, temperature and reaction time were investigated. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that a satisfactory result was obtained. Moreover, increasing temperature and CaO concentration, higher conversion rate was achieved and time does not seem to have any significant effect.

The statistical models developed for predicting yield showed a good agreement between the experimental and calculated values (≥ 0.97 and ≥ 0.95) for chicken eggshell CaO catalyst and periwinkle shells CaO catalyst respectively, demonstrating the usefulness of regression analysis as a tool for optimization purposes with chicken eggshell CaO catalyst R^2 value closer to unity denoting the catalyst with better yield.

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